

Comparison of Geostatistical and Machine Learning Methods for Spatial Analysis of Natural Resources Data

Maria Konstantina Germanou · Andreas Pavlides ·
Emmanouil A. Varouchakis

Received: date / Accepted: date

Abstract This research work employs advanced geostatistical and machine learning methods to analyze and model spatial data, with a focus on zinc concentration measurements. The primary objectives are to evaluate and compare these methods in terms of generating accurate spatial predictions, quantifying uncertainty, and identifying critical spatial patterns. The suggested approach used Self-Organizing Maps (SOM) to augment the applicability of Ordinary Kriging (OK) to a considerably large dataset. The classical OK approach and the Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) method were applied for comparison purposes, as they are widely used methods. All three methods satisfy both fields explored herein, geostatistics and machine learning.

In preliminary analysis, a variety of kernels were tested, including the novel Harmonic Covariance Estimator (HCE). The exponential kernel was selected for the comparisons among the three methods. GPR is a flexible Bayesian approach that is exceptionally efficient in capturing complex spatial patterns and providing robust uncertainty estimates. While both GPR and OK aim to achieve accurate spatial predictions, SOMs enhance kriging by classifying data and facilitating predictions based on the best-matching neuron's data, effectively adapting kriging to localized spatial patterns and improving the interpretability of spatial dependencies.

This integration of methodologies demonstrates the combination of stochastic geostatistical methods with machine learning for an improved understanding and prediction of spatial phenomena. The results highlight that this modeling approach enhances the management and evaluation of natural resources, specifically in the case of a zinciferous ore deposit. More specifically, the research findings indicated that the conventional selection of neighborhoods in OK tends to favor certain validation measures. In contrast, the SOM-guided selection of the neighborhood enhances the predictive-observational correlation.

1 Introduction

The integration of geostatistical methods with machine learning techniques has emerged as a transformative approach for analyzing and predicting complex geospatial data in various fields, including mining, environmental monitoring, and resource management. These datasets often exhibit intricate spatial patterns and dependencies, which are essential for accurate analysis but challenging to model. Traditional methods such as Ordinary Kriging (OK) are widely used for spatial prediction, since they effectively utilize the spatial correlations in observed data to make unbiased predictions through covariance or variogram modeling. However, while effective, OK and its variants suffer from significant limitations regarding non-stationary processes that are common in many complex datasets. These have been extensively discussed and analyzed by (Cressie 1993) and (Goovaerts 1997).

Rasmussen and Williams (2006) introduced Gaussian Process Regression (GPR) as a flexible probabilistic framework that captures nonlinear spatial patterns and provides robust uncertainty quantification, thereby addressing several challenges faced by traditional methods. Further emphasizing its utility, (Hengl et al. 2004) demonstrated the application of GPR in predicting soil properties such as organic carbon, texture classes, and nutrient distribution. Similarly, (Liu and Weisberg 2005) discussed the flexibility of GPR in modeling both groundwater quality and ocean current variability, thereby demonstrating its ability to adapt across diverse geospatial contexts.

An expansion of spatial analysis was proposed by (Kohonen 2001), who developed Self-Organizing Maps (SOM), an unsupervised learning algorithm. SOM transforms high-dimensional data into clustered and interpretable spatial structures. (Bação et al. 2005) demonstrated how SOM could serve as a substitute for k-Means clustering in the analysis of soil variability. Similarly, (Vesanto and Alhoniemi 2000) illustrated the use of SOM to cluster high-dimensional environmental data for identifying the sources of groundwater contamination. More generally, (Liu and Weisberg 2011) provided an extensive review of the applications of SOM in meteorology and oceanography, demonstrating its wide applicability in environmental sciences.

The potential of hybrid approaches that synergistically combine the strengths of GPR, SOM, and traditional geostatistical methods, such as OK, has been tried and tested, demonstrating their efficiency in enhancing geospatial data analysis. (Hengl et al. 2004) presented regression-kriging frameworks to improve predictions of soil variables. Further extensions in advanced geostatistics, integrated with machine learning techniques, have been made in hydrology and water resource management, where SOM-based clustering has been instrumental in assessing pollution patterns, as demonstrated by (Liu and Weisberg 2005) and (Vesanto and Alhoniemi 2000).

OK remains the most widely established stochastic geostatistical method, preferred by the geoscientific community (Cressie 1993; Chiles and Delfiner 2012) since its original formulation (Krige 1951; Matheron 1965). GPR can be regarded as a supervised machine learning counterpart to kriging, grounded in similar probabilistic principles. Given that SOM fall within the field of unsupervised learning, they were contrasted with GPR to compare their efficiency on spatial modeling. (Varouchakis et al. 2023) proposed a hybrid Geostat-SOM framework, which integrates SOM with OK to classify and then interpolate groundwater levels across complex hydrogeological systems.

The work examines the combined application of OK, GPR, and SOM to develop an integrated framework for spatial data analysis. From the various Kernels investigated in preliminary analysis (including the Harmonic Covariance Estimator), the Exponential Kernel performed better and is used in this work. The current research introduces an important improvement in the predictiveness and interpretation of spatial patterns by involving the complementarities of these methodologies. It examines OK and GPR for efficient spatial interpolation and uncertainty quantification, while SOM is used to guide kriging estimations by enhancing data classification. This integrated approach overcomes the intrinsic shortcomings of conventional geostatistical methods and provides a flexible methodology for geospatial analysis supporting sustainable resource management. The framework proposed in this research can be extended to different datasets so that follow-up research can augment geostatistical methodologies with machine learning models.

2 Methodology

2.1 Ordinary Kriging

Kriging refers to a group of stochastic interpolation methods that are by construction linear, unbiased, and minimum variance estimators (Goovaerts 1997; Varouchakis et al. 2018).

The value of the random field $X(\mathbf{u})$ at an unmeasured location $\mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{G}$ is estimated by a linear combination of the measurements at $n(\mathbf{u})$ nearby points $\mathbf{s}_1(\mathbf{u}), \dots, \mathbf{s}_{n(\mathbf{u})}$, where $\mathbf{s}_i(\mathbf{u}) \in \{\mathbf{s}_1, \dots, \mathbf{s}_N\}$ is a neighbor of \mathbf{u} for all $i = 1, \dots, n(\mathbf{u})$. A map of the spatial distribution of the field is obtained by repeating the estimation process at every node of a prediction grid. Such maps can be accompanied by estimates of the prediction variance at each point. The variance can adequately represent the prediction uncertainty if the data probability distribution is Gaussian. If the data follow a skewed probability distribution, the Kriging-based uncertainty estimates are not reliable (Pavlidis et al. 2022).

To reflect the spatial dependence of \mathbf{u} with each point in $n(\mathbf{u})$, the variogram is used. The variogram function $\gamma_x(\mathbf{r})$ for stationary random fields is connected to the covariance function $c_x(\mathbf{r})$ as shown in Eq. (1).

$$\gamma_x(\mathbf{r}) = c_x(0) - c_x(\mathbf{r}) \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{r} is the distance between two points. Thus, the variogram function can be used interchangeably with the covariance function if the random field is considered a stationary field.

The variogram function is defined as follows.

$$\gamma_x(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{1}{2} \text{Var}[X(\mathbf{s}) - X(\mathbf{s} + \mathbf{r})] \quad (2)$$

95 where Var is the variance operator, i.e., $\text{Var}(X) = \mathbb{E}[X^2(\mathbf{s})] - \mathbb{E}^2[X(\mathbf{s})]$ (Hristopoulos 2020).

96 OK assumes that the random field is stationary and its mean, m_X , is unknown, but constant within
97 the kriging neighborhood. The OK estimator is obtained by means of the following equation (Krige 1951;
98 Cressie 1990):

$$\hat{X}(\mathbf{u}) = \sum_{i=1}^{n(\mathbf{u})} \lambda_i(\mathbf{u}) (X_i) \quad (3)$$

99 In Eq. (3), $\lambda_i(\mathbf{u})$ are the Kriging weights at the target point \mathbf{u} . The Kriging weights are calculated
100 by solving the following linear system.

$$\mathbf{C}_x \boldsymbol{\Lambda} = \mathbf{C}_u \quad (4)$$

101 where \mathbf{C}_x is the covariance (or variogram) matrix of the fluctuation random field $X'(\cdot)$ at the data
102 locations, i.e., $[\mathbf{C}_x]_{i,j} = c(\mathbf{s}_i - \mathbf{s}_j)$ for $i, j = 1, \dots, n(\mathbf{u})$, $\boldsymbol{\Lambda} = (\lambda_1(\mathbf{u}), \dots, \lambda_{n(\mathbf{u})}(\mathbf{u}))^\top$ is the vector of the
103 Kriging weights, and $\mathbf{C}_u = (c(\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{s}_1), \dots, c(\mathbf{u} - \mathbf{s}_{n(\mathbf{u})}))^\top$ is the covariance (or variogram) vector between
104 the unknown point \mathbf{u} and each of the $n(\mathbf{u})$ neighbor points that contribute to the estimate (Chiles and
105 Delfiner 2012). The Kriging estimate $\hat{X}(\mathbf{u})$ at \mathbf{u} is obtained by replacing in Eq. (3) the X_i with the
106 respective data values, m_X with the estimate of the mean, and the Kriging weights with the solution of
107 Eq. (4) for $\boldsymbol{\Lambda}$.

108 2.2 Gaussian Process Regression

109 **GPR is a nonparametric, flexible regression that captures complex patterns in spatial data by modeling**
110 **correlations between data points using kernel functions.** A **Gaussian Process (GP)** is a collection of
111 random variables, any finite subset of which follows a joint multivariate Gaussian distribution. Formally,
112 a GP $\{f(\mathbf{x})\}_{\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{X}}$, indexed by an input space \mathcal{X} , is characterized by its mean function $m(\mathbf{x})$ and covariance
113 function $c(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')$, and can be written as:

$$f(\mathbf{x}) \sim \mathcal{GP}(m(\mathbf{x}), c(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')), \quad (5)$$

114 where:

- 115 – $m(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbb{E}[f(\mathbf{x})]$ is the mean function, which gives the expected value of the process at input \mathbf{x} ,
- 116 – $c(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') = \mathbb{E}[(f(\mathbf{x}) - m(\mathbf{x}))(f(\mathbf{x}') - m(\mathbf{x}'))]$ is the covariance function, which defines the relationship
117 (similarity) between function values at different input points \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{x}' .

118 These two components fully specify a Gaussian Process—the mean function and the covariance func-
119 tion. GPR provides a flexible, non-parametric framework for modeling functions, as they do not assume
120 a specific form of the function but instead defines a distribution over all possible functions that could
121 explain the observed data. **GPR assumes that the data points are drawn from a multivariate normal dis-**
122 **tribution and models the spatial structure of the data through the covariance (kernel) function mentioned**
123 **above.**

124 Due to its analytical tractability, the GP is commonly used to model real-valued functions, particularly
125 in cases where uncertainty needs to be quantified. In practice, one can think of a GP as a distribution
126 over functions, where any collection of function values has a multivariate Gaussian distribution.

127 2.2.1 The Covariance Function (Kernel)

128 The covariance function, also known as the kernel function, is a fundamental component of GPR. It
129 defines the covariance between function values at different input points, controlling key properties of
130 the resulting function such as smoothness, periodicity, and behavior over various scales. Formally, the
131 covariance function $c(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')$ takes two input points \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{x}' and returns a scalar that represents the
132 covariance between the corresponding function values, $f(\mathbf{x})$ and $f(\mathbf{x}')$.

133 A covariance (kernel) function $c(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')$ is a non-negative, real-valued, integrable function that repre-
134 sents a mapping $\mathbb{R}^d \times \mathbb{R}^d \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. Let \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{x}' be two points in the \mathbb{R}^d Euclidean space, and let $u = \|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'\|$
135 represent the Euclidean distance between them (Hristopoulos 2020). A covariance function satisfies the
136 following properties:

- 137 1. **Non-negativity:** $c(u) \geq 0$ for all u .

- 138 2. **Symmetry:** $c(u) = c(-u)$ for all u .
 139 3. **Normalization:** $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} du c(u) = 1$.
 140 4. **Finite second-order moment:** The integral $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} du u^2 c(u)$ exists.
 141 5. **Mode at the origin:** $c(u)$ takes its maximum value at $u = 0$.
 142 6. **Continuity:** $c(u)$ is a continuous function of u .
 143 7. **Scaling:** If $c(u)$ is a covariance function and $h > 0$ is a non-negative number, then the function
 144 $c_h(u) = \frac{1}{h} c\left(\frac{u}{h}\right)$ is also a covariance function.

145 *Models of Covariance Functions:*

146 Commonly used models of covariance functions are listed below. These functions depend on the normal-
 147 ized distance $u = \frac{\|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'\|}{h}$, where $h > 0$ represents the kernel bandwidth.

148 For radial kernels, the covariance functions depend only on the magnitude $u = \|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'\|$, not the
 149 direction of the Euclidean distance between two points.

- 150 1. **Uniform:**

$$c(u) = \frac{1}{2} \mathbb{I}_{|u| \leq 1}(u). \quad (6)$$

- 151 2. **Spherical:**

$$c(u) = \frac{4}{3} (1 - 1.5u + 0.5u^3) \mathbb{I}_{|u| \leq 1}(u). \quad (7)$$

- 152 3. **Gaussian:**

$$c(u) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp(-u^2). \quad (8)$$

- 153 4. **Exponential:**

$$c(u) = \frac{1}{2} \exp(-|u|). \quad (9)$$

154 In the above, $\mathbb{I}_{|u| \leq 1}(u)$ denotes the indicator function, which satisfies:

$$\mathbb{I}_{|u| \leq 1}(u) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } |u| \leq 1, \\ 0 & \text{if } |u| > 1. \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

155 The first two covariance functions are compactly supported, meaning they are zero outside the interval
 156 $|u| \leq 1$, while the last two have unbounded support.

157 *2.2.2 Harmonic Covariance Estimator (HCE)*

158 A novel covariance function, the Harmonic Covariance Estimator (HCE) has been developed and detailed
 159 in (Varouchakis et al. 2025). HCE is based on the Spatiotemporal covariance functions from spatial
 160 physics and specifically from the Linearly Damped Harmonic Oscillator (LDHO) (Hristopoulos 2024).
 161 The equation of HCE is shown in eq. (11) below:

$$c(u) = \frac{\eta_0^2 \Gamma\left(\frac{d+1}{2}\right) \beta}{\pi^{\frac{d+1}{2}} (u^2 + \beta^2)^{\frac{d+1}{2}}}, \quad (11)$$

162 where d is the number of dimensions, η_0^2 is a scaling factor, and β is a parameter that controls the rate
 163 of the decay of the kernel with distance. HCE has been used in various natural resources applications,
 164 utilizing Euclidean and non-Euclidean distances.

165 *2.2.3 Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE)*

166 Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE) is a commonly used method for selecting the parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta} \in \Theta$
 167 of a parameterized covariance kernel $c_{\boldsymbol{\theta}}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')$ (Rasmussen and Williams 2006). Under the Gaussian
 168 Process model $\mathcal{GP}(m, c_{\boldsymbol{\theta}})$, the probability density function of the observed data \mathbf{y} given $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ is expressed
 169 as:

$$p(\mathbf{y}|\boldsymbol{\theta}) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\det(2\pi\mathbf{C})}} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2}\mathbf{y}^\top \mathbf{C}^{-1}\mathbf{y}\right), \quad (12)$$

170 Where:

171 – \mathbf{y} : The observed target values,

- 172 – \mathbf{C} : The covariance matrix computed using the kernel $c_{\boldsymbol{\theta}}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')$ for the observed inputs \mathbf{x} ,
- 173 – $\boldsymbol{\theta}$: Parameters of the kernel (e.g., length scale, variance, nugget).

174 Maximizing this likelihood function is equivalent to minimizing the negative log-likelihood function.
 175 The log-likelihood function is given by:

$$\log p(\mathbf{y}|\boldsymbol{\theta}) = -\frac{1}{2}\mathbf{y}^\top \mathbf{C}^{-1}\mathbf{y} - \frac{1}{2}\log \det \mathbf{C} - \frac{n}{2}\log(2\pi), \quad (13)$$

176 Where n is the number of observed data points.

177 For computational convenience, we often minimize the **modified log-likelihood function**, which
 178 removes constant terms:

$$l(\boldsymbol{\theta}|\mathbf{y}) = \mathbf{y}^\top \mathbf{C}^{-1}\mathbf{y} + \log \det \mathbf{C}. \quad (14)$$

179 2.2.4 Optimization of Kernel Parameters

180 The parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ are selected by solving:

$$\boldsymbol{\theta}_{\text{ML}} \in \arg \min_{\boldsymbol{\theta} \in \Theta} l(\boldsymbol{\theta}|\mathbf{y}), \quad (15)$$

181 Where:

- 182 – The first term $\mathbf{y}^\top \mathbf{C}^{-1}\mathbf{y}$ measures the goodness-of-fit of the model to the data,
- 183 – The second term $\log \det \mathbf{C}$ penalizes model complexity to prevent overfitting.

184 By minimizing this objective function, MLE balances the trade-off between model fit and complexity,
 185 ensuring that the selected kernel parameters $\boldsymbol{\theta}$ generalize well to unseen data. This process is critical
 186 for accurately modeling the covariance structure $c(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')$ between observed data \mathbf{x} and unobserved test
 187 points \mathbf{x}' .

188 2.2.5 Constructing the Gaussian Process

189 To model a set of data $T = \{(\mathbf{x}_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^n$, we can employ a GP. This provides a flexible, nonlinear
 190 alternative to simple linear regression models, such as $Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X + \epsilon$, which may not fully capture
 191 the complexity of the data (Rasmussen and Williams 2006). Instead of assuming a linear relationship,
 192 we hypothesize a nonlinear function \mathbf{f} that maps inputs to outputs via the model:

$$y_i = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_i) + \epsilon_i, \quad (16)$$

193 where ϵ_i represents noise or observation error, typically assumed to be independent and identically
 194 distributed (i.i.d.) according to:

$$\epsilon_i \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \sigma_n^2), \quad (17)$$

195 with σ_n^2 being the noise variance.

196 In GPs, the function values $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x})$ and $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}')$ for any two distinct known inputs \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{x}' are treated
 197 as random variables that follow a joint Gaussian distribution. This assumption allows us to model the
 198 correlation between function values at different input locations.

199 The joint distribution of the function values at known inputs \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{x}' can be written as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) \\ \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}') \end{bmatrix} \sim \mathcal{N} \left(\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{m}(\mathbf{x}) \\ \mathbf{m}(\mathbf{x}') \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{c}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}) & \mathbf{c}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') \\ \mathbf{c}(\mathbf{x}', \mathbf{x}) & \mathbf{c}(\mathbf{x}', \mathbf{x}') \end{bmatrix} \right), \quad (18)$$

200 where $\mathbf{m}(\mathbf{x})$ and $\mathbf{m}(\mathbf{x}')$ are the mean function values at the known inputs \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{x}' , and $\mathbf{c}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')$ is the
 201 covariance between the function values at \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{x}' .

202 A GP is formally defined as a collection of random variables, any finite subset of which follows a
 203 joint multivariate Gaussian distribution. Thus, for a finite set of known inputs $\{\mathbf{x}^{(1)}, \mathbf{x}^{(2)}, \dots, \mathbf{x}^{(n)}\}$, the
 204 corresponding function values $\{\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}^{(1)}), \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}^{(2)}), \dots, \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}^{(n)})\}$ are jointly distributed as:

$$\mathbf{f} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}^{(1)}) \\ \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}^{(2)}) \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}^{(n)}) \end{bmatrix} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{m}, \mathbf{C}), \quad (19)$$

205 where \mathbf{m} is the mean vector and \mathbf{C} is the covariance matrix derived from the covariance function $\mathbf{c}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')$,
 206 also known as the kernel. This covariance function governs the relationships between the function values
 207 at different known inputs.

208 If the target function $f(x)$ is estimated as a GP, then one needs to check if the consistency requirement
 209 of the estimator is fulfilled (Papoulis 1991). One can easily do this by the marginalization property of
 210 multivariate Gaussian distributions. The marginalization property tells us that if

$$(\mathbf{f}_1, \mathbf{f}_2) \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{m}, \mathbf{C}), \quad (20)$$

211 Then we also have

$$\mathbf{f}_1 \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{m}_1, \mathbf{C}_{11}), \quad \mathbf{f}_2 \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{m}_2, \mathbf{C}_{22}), \quad (21)$$

212 where \mathbf{C}_{11} and \mathbf{C}_{22} are sub-matrices of \mathbf{C} .

213 2.2.6 The Prior in GPR

214 In GPR, the **prior** encodes assumptions about the underlying function before any data is observed
 215 (Rasmussen and Williams 2006). Two key components specify the prior:

- 216 – A **mean function**, $m(\mathbf{x})$, typically indicating no prior knowledge about the function's value before
 217 data is observed. Often, it is assumed to be zero, i.e., $m(\mathbf{x}) = 0$.
- 218 – A **covariance function** or kernel, $c(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')$, which defines the correlation between function values at
 219 different input points.

220 The function we wish to model is assumed to be drawn from a Gaussian process:

$$f(\mathbf{x}) \sim \mathcal{GP}(m(\mathbf{x}) = 0, c(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')), \quad (22)$$

221 Where $f(\mathbf{x})$ represents the function, $m(\mathbf{x}) = 0$ is the mean function (often assumed to be zero), and
 222 $c(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')$ is the covariance function, which controls the structure and smoothness of the function.

223 The GP *prior* describes a distribution over possible functions, before any observations are made.
 224 Specifically, the prior assumes that any finite set of function values follows a **joint Gaussian distri-**
 225 **bution**, meaning that the values of $f(\mathbf{x}_1), f(\mathbf{x}_2), \dots, f(\mathbf{x}_N)$ for different input points $\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, \dots, \mathbf{x}_N$ are
 226 jointly distributed according to a multivariate Gaussian.

227 In summary, the GP prior encapsulates our beliefs about the range of possible functions the model
 228 can represent, with the covariance function dictating how function values are related across the input
 229 space.

230 2.2.7 Constructing the GPR

231 GPR assumes that the function we wish to model, denoted $f(\cdot)$, is drawn from a Gaussian process
 232 (Murphy 2012). Given a set of training inputs $\mathbf{X} = \{\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, \dots, \mathbf{x}_N\}$ and corresponding observed function
 233 values $\mathbf{f} = \{f(\mathbf{x}_1), f(\mathbf{x}_2), \dots, f(\mathbf{x}_N)\}$, the goal is to predict the function value $f(\mathbf{x}_0)$ at a new test input
 234 \mathbf{x}_0 .

235 To achieve this, we model the joint distribution of the function values at the training points and
 236 the test point. This distribution is Gaussian and described by a mean function $m(\cdot)$ and a covariance
 237 function $c(\cdot, \cdot)$ (also known as the kernel function).

238 The joint distribution of the function values $f(\mathbf{x})$ at the training points $\{\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2, \dots, \mathbf{x}_N\}$ and the test
 239 point \mathbf{x}_0 can be expressed as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} f(\mathbf{x}_1) \\ \vdots \\ f(\mathbf{x}_N) \\ f(\mathbf{x}_0) \end{bmatrix} \sim \mathcal{N} \left(\begin{bmatrix} m(\mathbf{x}_1) \\ \vdots \\ m(\mathbf{x}_N) \\ m(\mathbf{x}_0) \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} c(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_1) & \cdots & c(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_N) & c(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_0) \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ c(\mathbf{x}_N, \mathbf{x}_1) & \cdots & c(\mathbf{x}_N, \mathbf{x}_N) & c(\mathbf{x}_N, \mathbf{x}_0) \\ c(\mathbf{x}_0, \mathbf{x}_1) & \cdots & c(\mathbf{x}_0, \mathbf{x}_N) & c(\mathbf{x}_0, \mathbf{x}_0) \end{bmatrix} \right), \quad (23)$$

240 Where:

- 241 – $m(\mathbf{x}_i)$ is the mean of the Gaussian process at the point \mathbf{x}_i ,
- 242 – $c(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j)$ is the covariance between the function values $f(\mathbf{x}_i)$ and $f(\mathbf{x}_j)$, and it is determined by the
 243 chosen kernel function,
- 244 – $\mathcal{N}(\mathbf{m}, \mathbf{C})$ represents the multivariate normal distribution with mean vector \mathbf{m} and covariance matrix
 245 \mathbf{C} .

2.2.8 Posterior Distribution

To predict the function value $f(\mathbf{x}_0)$ at the test point \mathbf{x}_0 , we compute the posterior distribution by conditioning the joint distribution of the training data and test point on the observed values at the training points (Duvenaud 2014). The posterior distribution of $f(\mathbf{x}_0)$, given the observed training data $f(X)$, is a Gaussian distribution with the following mean and variance:

Posterior Mean:

$$\mathbb{E}[f(\mathbf{x}_0)|f(X)] = m(\mathbf{x}_0) + C(\mathbf{x}_0, X)C(X, X)^{-1}(f(X) - m(X)), \quad (24)$$

where:

- $m(\mathbf{x}_0)$ is the prior mean of the function value at the test point \mathbf{x}_0 ,
- $C(\mathbf{x}_0, X)$ is the vector of covariances between the test point \mathbf{x}_0 and the training points $\{\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_N\}$, i.e., $C(\mathbf{x}_0, X) = [c(\mathbf{x}_0, \mathbf{x}_1), \dots, c(\mathbf{x}_0, \mathbf{x}_N)]$,
- $C(X, X)$ is the covariance matrix of the function values at the training points, with (i, j) -th entry given by $c(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{x}_j)$,
- $f(X) = [f(\mathbf{x}_1), \dots, f(\mathbf{x}_N)]^T$ is the vector of observed function values at the training points,
- $m(X) = [m(\mathbf{x}_1), \dots, m(\mathbf{x}_N)]^T$ is the mean vector of the function values at the training points.

The posterior mean $\mathbb{E}[f(\mathbf{x}_0)|f(X)]$ represents the best estimate of the function value at the test point \mathbf{x}_0 based on the training data. It is a linear combination of the observed values $f(X)$, where the weights depend on the kernel function and the relative distances between the test point and the training points.

Posterior Variance:

$$\text{Var}[f(\mathbf{x}_0)|f(X)] = c(\mathbf{x}_0, \mathbf{x}_0) - C(\mathbf{x}_0, X)C(X, X)^{-1}C(X, \mathbf{x}_0), \quad (25)$$

where:

- $c(\mathbf{x}_0, \mathbf{x}_0)$ is the prior variance (i.e., the variance without observing any data) of the function value at the test point \mathbf{x}_0 ,
- $C(\mathbf{x}_0, X)C(X, X)^{-1}C(X, \mathbf{x}_0)$ is the reduction in uncertainty due to the information provided by the observed data.

The posterior distribution incorporates information from observed data points (red dots), resulting in low variance and high confidence near these points. Further from the training points, the model's uncertainty increases, as indicated by the higher variance. Thus, the posterior variance reflects the model's confidence, decreasing near known data and remaining high in less-sampled regions.

2.2.9 Prediction

The posterior distribution enables predictions at new test points \mathbf{x}_0 based on training data $\{\mathbf{x}_1, \dots, \mathbf{x}_N\}$. The posterior mean $\mathbb{E}[f(\mathbf{x}_0)|f(X)]$ serves as the point estimate, while the posterior variance $\text{Var}[f(\mathbf{x}_0)|f(X)]$ reflects prediction uncertainty.

With a Gaussian process and a covariance function like the **exponential kernel of Eq. (9) or Eq. (11)**, predictions are smooth and continuous. This dual output of prediction and uncertainty makes GPR ideal for applications like **natural resources reserves estimation**, where high uncertainty indicates areas that may need further data.

2.3 Self-Organizing Map (SOM) Algorithm

The Self-Organizing Map (SOM), developed by Teuvo Kohonen, is an unsupervised learning algorithm that projects high-dimensional data onto a lower-dimensional grid while maintaining the topological properties of the input space (Villmann and Bauer 1998).

2.3.1 SOM Architecture

The SOM is composed of one input layer and one feature map layer in a two-dimensional space, where every neuron in the feature map is connected to all the input dimensions via weight vectors (Kohonen and Honkela 2011; Kohonen 2005). The SOM projects high-dimensional input data onto a lower-dimensional map while maintaining topological relationships. In training, for every input vector, the Best Matching Unit (BMU) is determined by using a similarity measure, such as Euclidean distance, and the weights of the BMU and its neighbors are iteratively updated. Over time, the SOM self-organizes so that similar input vectors are mapped to neighboring neurons, thereby preserving the topology and density of the input space.

Fig. 1: Self-Organizing Map (SOM) architecture (modified after (Karimi et al. 2023)).

Fig. 1 shows how the SOM maps the high-dimensional input space into an orderly two-dimensional map: **Input vectors are mapped to a two-dimensional feature map. The BMU and its neighboring neurons are updated iteratively, enabling the SOM to approximate the input space topology.** That makes SOMs applicable to clustering and reduction of dimensionality problems, as well as the visualization of complex datasets containing nonlinear relationships, which appear more effective than PCA due to its linearity.

2.3.2 SOM Algorithm

The SOM algorithm iteratively organizes the input data onto a grid. Below is presented a step-by-step layout for the implementation of the algorithm:

- **Step 1:** Each neuron's weight vector \mathbf{w}_j is initialized randomly over the input space.
- **Step 2:** For each iteration k , a random input vector $\mathbf{x}(k)$ is selected from the dataset. Here, k represents the current iteration number in the training process.
- **Step 3:** The BMU is identified by finding the neuron whose weight vector is closest to $\mathbf{x}(k)$ in terms of Euclidean distance:

$$\mathbf{w}_{\text{BMU}}(k) = \min_j \|\mathbf{x}(k) - \mathbf{w}_j(k)\|. \quad (26)$$

- **Step 4:** The weights of the BMU and its neighbors are updated to move closer to $\mathbf{x}(k)$:

$$\mathbf{w}_j(k+1) = \mathbf{w}_j(k) + \theta(j, \text{BMU}, k) \cdot \alpha(k) \cdot (\mathbf{x}(k) - \mathbf{w}_j(k)), \quad (27)$$

Where:

- $\alpha(k)$ is the learning rate, decreasing over iterations,
- $\theta(j, \text{BMU}, k)$ is the neighborhood function, which decreases with distance from the BMU and with k .
- **Step 5:** Repeat the steps for all iterations, gradually reducing $\alpha(k)$ and the neighborhood radius $\sigma(k)$ over time until the map stabilizes.

where k represents the iteration index of the training process. Each iteration corresponds to one step in adapting the SOM to the input data, and k progresses from 1 to the total number of iterations.

Once training is complete, the SOM provides an organized map that reflects the structure of the input space, grouping similar data and preserving topological relationships. This enables effective clustering and visualization of high-dimensional data (Haykin 2009).

2.3.3 Optimal Map Size

For proper clustering and correct representation of the data set, different SOM grid configurations should be considered. When choosing a suitable map size, the aim is to achieve optimal preservation of spatial relationships in the dataset by minimizing corresponding errors. Therefore, any map size has been considered in terms of two main performance metrics:

- **Quantization Error (QE):** Quantization Error measures the average Euclidean distance between each data point and its nearest neuron, also known as the Best Matching Unit (BMU). A lower QE indicates that the neurons within the grid effectively capture and represent the data’s intrinsic characteristics, improving clustering quality.
- **Topographic Error (TE):** Topographic Error measures the extent to which the SOM preserves the topological structure of the dataset. It is defined as the proportion of data points for which the first and second closest neurons (BMUs) are not adjacent. A lower TE suggests that the map maintains the spatial continuity of the data, which is crucial for accurate spatial pattern recognition.

2.3.4 OK Estimation with SOM Neurons

One of the goals of this research is to present how SOM can be combined with kriging methods to improve the neighborhood selection, specifically with OK. The methodology for OK estimation using SOM neurons involves:

1. **Data Grouping with SOM:** Apply SOM to cluster data points into neurons based on similarity, organizing spatial data into a grid for local pattern capture.
2. **Selecting Nearest Neurons:** For each prediction location (X_p, Y_p) , identify the nearest neurons. Use data from these neurons to inform the kriging estimation, ensuring local influence is maintained.
3. **OK with Localized Data:** Apply OK using data from selected neurons. Model spatial correlation with a variogram to weight data points according to their distance from (X_p, Y_p) , yielding localized predictions.
4. **Generating the Spatial Prediction Map:** Create a continuous prediction map by applying kriging across all target locations.

Sparse regions in the dataset can result in empty neurons, leading to unreliable or incomplete predictions. Aggregating data from the k nearest neurons (herein $k = 5$) mitigates this issue by incorporating information from neighboring regions, ensuring robust predictions even in areas with fewer data points.

3 Case Study and preliminary steps

The data of this case study are drawn from the Geoscience Regulation Office (GSRO) of the Department of the Environment, Climate and Communications of the Republic of Ireland. GSRO was established in January 2021 and provides a large list of historical mining data (Geoscience Regulation Office Information Hub 2021).

The dataset used in this case study consists of values from 633 exploratory drill holes, representing Zinc concentration with a range from 30.0 to 6988.3 ppm, a median of 189.0 ppm, and a mean of 158.5 ppm. The coordinates of the original data are in the Irish Transverse Mercator (ITM) system, expressed in kilometers, and have been converted to the same unit for ease of use. The drill locations are presented in Fig. 2. The data in question are in <http://gofile.me/75XIE/uBX1jglCy>. The analysis is conducted with the logarithm of the concentration with units of log of ppm. Thus, the range of the variable values is from 3.40 to 8.85, with a median of 5.24 and a mean of 5.07, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Zinc concentration summary statistics.

Statistic	Zn (ppm)	log(Zn)
Minimum	30.0	3.40
Maximum	6988.3	8.85
Mean	158.5	5.07
Median	189.0	5.24

Fig. 2: Sampling locations

3.1 Linear Trend Model

The zinc concentration $Z(x)$ at a location $x = (X, Y)$ can be modeled as:

$$m(x) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X + \beta_2 Y, \quad (28)$$

Where:

Table 2: Linear Trend Model Coefficients

Parameter	Value
β_0 (Intercept)	-284.825
β_1 (Coefficient for X)	0.55
β_2 (Coefficient for Y)	-0.06

The positive coefficient for X indicates that zinc concentration increases with Easting, while the negative coefficient for Y suggests a slight decrease with Northing. Table 2 summarises the derived coefficients from the fitting of the linear model.

Detrending is crucial for accurate spatial modeling. Removing the large-scale trend allows the interpolation to focus on local spatial correlations. Reintroducing the trend in final predictions ensures both overall trends and regional variations in zinc concentration are considered, leading to more reliable spatial estimates.

372 4 Results & Discussion

373 4.1 Ordinary Kriging results

374 Figure 3 displays the OK map of the spatial prediction for zinc concentrations. Unlike GPR, we have
 375 used a kriging neighborhood of 300m. The plot uses a logarithmic scale, while the colorbar displays the
 376 values in the original concentration scale, ranging from 30 ppm to 7000 ppm. This visualization high-
 377 lights spatial patterns, showing high-concentration "hotspots" and low-concentration areas, enhancing
 378 the interpretation of spatial variability.

379 One notices strong hotspots of zinc in the central parts of the area studied, with high concentrations
 380 recorded in this region. In general, this central area of high values would indicate a high concentration of
 381 Zn, as one would expect from a Zn/Pb mine. Surrounding this hotspot are areas of lower concentration,
 382 reflecting spatial variability across the landscape.

Fig. 3: Spatial prediction map of zinc concentrations using OK. Values in ppm.

383 To evaluate the predictive accuracy of OK, Leave-One-Out Cross-Validation (LOOCV) was employed,
 384 after back-transforming the logarithm data to ppm. This method systematically omits each data point in
 385 turn from the training set and then predicts the value at the excluded location. Such a process provides a
 386 comprehensive and unbiased estimate of prediction error across individual data points, thereby enhancing
 387 the confidence that the model indeed generalizes well. **The LOOCV results are presented in table 3.**

Table 3: Performance Metrics of OK. RMSE: Root Mean Square Error, MAE: Mean Absolute Error, ME: Mean Error, ρ : Pearson's correlation coefficient.

Metric	OK
RMSE (ppm)	485.79
MAE (ppm)	186.97
ME (ppm)	-71.9
ρ	0.76

388 4.2 GPR results

389 GPR was applied to model the spatial relationships between zinc concentrations and their spatial coordinates.
 390

After considering the performance of kernels mentioned in Varouchakis et al. (2025) and HCE, the **Exponential Kernel** was selected, based on preliminary analysis using OK. For the Euclidean distance metric, while HCE performs better than the exponential in terms of the correlation coefficient (78% for HCE, compared to 76% for the exponential), it has a slightly higher RMSE. Thus, as both kernels align well with the type of spatial behavior in this dataset, the **Exponential Kernel was preferred**. By allowing a different length scale (range parameter), the Exponential Kernel models anisotropic spatial dependencies similarly to an exponential variogram applied in geostatistics. It assumes a decaying correlation between two points, depending on the distance between the points, in a truly exponential manner, which can explain spatial relations within the zinc data.

The kernel parameters, including signal variance, length scales, and noise variance, were optimized using **Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE)**. This method ensures the best fit to the observed data by maximizing the likelihood of the data under the Gaussian Process model.

Using the Exponential Kernel, GPR will provide an accurate model of the spatial correlation structure and give robust predictions of zinc concentrations at unsampled locations. GPR also provides a proper estimate of the uncertainty associated with each prediction, thus fully characterizing the reliability of the results.

The section presents the findings derived from applying GPR to the zinc concentration dataset and conducts a comparative analysis with OK. Emphasis is placed on evaluating predictive accuracy to assess the strengths and limitations inherent in each approach critically.

4.2.1 GPR Plot Analysis

The Figure 4 displays a map of the spatial prediction for zinc concentrations generated by means of GPR. One notices strong hotspots of zinc in the central parts of the area studied, with high concentrations recorded in this region. In general, this central hotspot would be indicative of significant zinc accumulation, and such may invite an investigation into the causes behind this concentration. Surrounding this hotspot are areas of lower concentration, reflecting spatial variability across the landscape. This map shows the notable concentrations of zinc, especially in the central part of the study area, with elevated levels. This hot spot in the center would be considered to reflect a very high accumulation of zinc, which could be suspected for a more detailed study of its underlying causes. There are areas with lower concentration surrounding this hot spot, which implies spatial variability across the landscape.

To evaluate the predictive accuracy of the GPR model for zinc concentrations within the study area, Leave-One-Out Cross-Validation (LOOCV) was employed.

This method systematically omits each data point in turn from the training set, allowing the GPR model to be trained on the remaining data and then used to predict the value at the excluded location. Such a process gives a comprehensive and unbiased estimate of prediction error across individual data points and enhances the confidence that the model indeed generalizes well. The integration of LOOCV within GPR is beneficial in this spatial analysis, as verification that the spatial patterns observed, such as regions of high concentrations of zinc ("hotspots"), reflect real trends and do not represent possible overfitting. In addition, the LOOCV provides insight into the model's spatial parameterization, guiding refinements to achieve a more accurate and reliable representation of the spatial variability of Zn concentrations.

The results in Table 4 show the validation metrics (after LOOCV) of GPR. We can see that compared to the range of values (30-7000 ppm), RMSE, MAE, and ME are acceptably low. Correlation ρ is 73%, showing a strong correlation between the observed and predicted values, which can also be seen in the scatterplot of Fig. 13.

Table 4: Performance Metrics of GPR. RMSE: Root Mean Square Error, MAE: Mean Absolute Error, ME: Mean Error, ρ : Pearson's correlation coefficient.

Metric	GPR
RMSE (ppm)	532.14
MAE (ppm)	190.46
ME (ppm)	-95.88
ρ	0.73

Fig. 4: Spatial prediction map of zinc concentrations using GPR. Values in ppm.

4.3 Self-Organizing Map (SOM) Method

SOM is a major unsupervised neural network algorithm that maps nonlinearly high-dimensional input data onto a structured grid. The SOM helps visualize complicated datasets and clustering data that are spatially correlated, hence capturing the underlying patterns while maintaining the topological relationships in data. In this work, a three-dimensional SOM is used for the analysis of the spatial distribution of zinc concentrations across the study area, considering spatial coordinates together with zinc concentration as input features. This way, it is guaranteed that both spatial and attribute-based patterns will be effectively grasped during clustering.

To identify an optimal balance between QE and TE (see Sec. 2.3.3), SOM map sizes ranging from 4×5 to 12×14 were tested. Based on these results, the 5×6 grid size was then determined to be the optimal configuration after observing these results because this choice struck a good balance between accurate data representation and topological preservation. The resolution of this grid is enough for spatial analysis and does not add unnecessary computational overhead.

4.3.1 Training Progress and Performance

Since the best map size was determined, the spatial coordinates of the zinc concentration data were used to train the SOM. Each data point was matched to its Best Matching Unit on the grid during training. Iteratively, the weights of the BMU and the weights of its neighboring neurons were updated as an approximation to the input data. Due to this adaptation process, the SOM could progressively organize similar coordinates of space into a cluster representative of different zinc concentration patterns.

A series of plots is used to evaluate the SOM's performance, illustrating how well the model organizes the zinc concentration data:

SOM Topology

The SOM topology plot in Figure 5 visually represents the structure of the Self-Organizing Map (SOM) and the arrangement of its neurons:

Fig. 5: SOM topology plot showing the arrangement of neurons in a hexagonal grid.

459 Neurons are organized in a hexagonal grid to allow flexible neighborhood connections, enhancing
 460 continuity between adjacent neurons. Each hexagon symbolizes a neuron, designed to preserve the topo-
 461 logical relationships of the input data, where similar data points are mapped close to each other.

462 This plot visually represents the spatial organization of neurons, supporting clustering by grouping
 463 similar data points. Here, a uniform color highlights the structural arrangement rather than individual
 464 data values. In other cases, colors can distinguish clusters or represent specific data values linked to each
 465 neuron.

466 The SOM topology plot provides insights into the map's ability to represent the dataset's structure,
 467 revealing clustering patterns and spatial relationships within the input data.

468 *SOM Neighbor Connections*

469 The SOM neighbor connections plot visualizes the topological relationships between neurons in the Self-
 470 Organizing Map (SOM) after training. In Figure 6, the blue circles represent neurons, and the red lines
 471 indicate the connections between neurons based on their proximity in the input data space.

Fig. 6: SOM Neighbor Connections plot, illustrating the topological relationships between neurons in the SOM grid. The red lines represent the connectivity between neurons.

472 Each blue circle represents a neuron, which corresponds to a cluster of input data points in the
 473 feature space. These neurons reflect how the input data points are distributed across the grid. The red
 474 lines between neurons depict the connections between neighboring neurons based on their proximity in
 475 the data space. Neurons with closer connections have more similar weight vectors, meaning they represent

476 more similar regions of the input space. The hexagonal grid preserves the topological properties of the
 477 input data, ensuring that data points with similar properties are mapped to neurons that are close
 478 together in the grid. Areas with fewer connections or neurons indicate regions in the input space where
 479 the data is less dense. These sparse regions suggest lower data concentration in the corresponding parts
 480 of the feature space.

481 The density of neurons in the grid and the strength of the connections between them give an idea
 482 of how well the SOM has captured the relationships within the data. This visualization helps identify
 483 clusters and regions with similar data points while preserving the overall structure of the input space.

484 *SOM Neighbor Distances*

485 The SOM neighbor distances plot in Figure 7 visualizes the distances between neighboring neurons, with
 486 color coding to indicate similarity:

Fig. 7: SOM Neighbor Distances plot, where darker colors represent larger distances between neighboring neurons, aiding in cluster and boundary identification.

487 Darker colors represent larger distances, hence boundaries or transition zones between clusters where
 488 data points are dissimilar. Lighter colors represent smaller distances, thus areas of high similarity and
 489 continuity.

490 This plot allows for easy identification of clusters and their boundaries, with darker regions drawing
 491 on separations between clusters and lighter regions indicating zones of homogeneity.

492 *SOM Sample Hits Plot*

493 The Self-Organizing Map (SOM) Sample Hits Plot, shown in Figure 8, illustrates how frequently each
 494 neuron in the SOM grid was selected as the Best Matching Unit (BMU) during the training phase.

495 Each hexagonal cell represents one neuron, and the number inside each cell indicates how many input
 496 data points are mapped to it. Neurons with high hit counts represent regions where input data is dense,
 497 and neurons with low hit counts correspond to sparsely populated areas in the input data space. In this
 498 plot, the neurons with high hit counts, such as 34, 32, and 29, are mainly located in the lower and central
 499 regions of the SOM grid. These neurons correspond to densely populated areas of the input data space
 500 where many input points have similar characteristics. On the other hand, neurons with relatively lower
 501 hit counts, like 7, 12, and 14, fall into the upper regions of the grid, indicating areas with sparse input
 502 data.

503 The distribution of hit counts across the SOM grid reflects how the input data is clustered. Regions
 504 with a high concentration of high hit counts reflect dense clusters, while neurons with low hit counts
 505 often indicate loosely scattered data points or outliers. A well-trained SOM should be characterized by a
 506 well-balanced distribution of hits that precisely reflect the density and structure of the input data space.

507 The Sample Hits Plot is a vital validation tool that shows the performance of the SOM. It confirms
 508 that the SOM is correctly modeling the density and distribution of the input data, outlines the clusters

Fig. 8: SOM Sample Hits Plot showing the number of times each neuron was selected as the Best Matching Unit (BMU) during training.

509 of similar data points, and finds sparse regions. This visualization ensures that the SOM effectively
 510 represents the patterns in the dataset, capturing both dense clusters and less populated areas.

511 *SOM Input Planes*

512 The Self-Organizing Map (SOM) input planes provide a visual representation of how each input feature
 513 contributes to the neurons in the SOM grid.

Fig. 9: SOM Input Planes showing the mapping of different input variables to the SOM neurons. Each plane corresponds to an individual input variable. The third input plane corresponds to the zinc concentration.

514 Each input plane corresponds to a specific input variable and illustrates how the values of that variable
 515 are distributed across the neurons. The color of each hexagonal cell represents the weight associated with
 516 a particular input feature, with darker colors indicating higher weights. This visualization helps identify
 517 the influence of each input feature on the SOM.

518 In Figure 9, the input planes represent three features. The first input plane shows the influence of the
 519 X spatial coordinate, where darker regions indicate neurons associated with higher X -values. Similarly,
 520 the second input plane corresponds to the Y spatial coordinate, and darker regions highlight neurons
 521 influenced by higher Y -values. The third input plane represents zinc concentrations, with darker regions
 522 revealing areas of higher zinc levels. These input planes collectively illustrate how the SOM captures
 523 spatial and attribute-based variability within the dataset.

524 By comparing these input planes, the relationships between features can be observed. For those
 525 regions with similar patterns across planes, such as overlapping darker areas, it means that there are
 526 correlated features that influence the same neurons. On the other hand, regions of dissimilar patterns
 527 indicate that different features contribute independently to the structure of the SOM. Such comparisons
 528 give insight into how spatial and concentration patterns interact within the dataset. The SOM input
 529 planes serve as a validation tool to understand the model's behavior. They show the features' relevance
 530 to the SOM's structure and allow the cluster identification, where some neurons respond vigorously
 531 to specific feature values. Moreover, the comparison between input planes enables the identification of
 532 correlations/contrasts between variables, making it useful to understand which relationships underlie the
 533 data.

534 *SOM Weight Positions*

535 The SOM Weight Positions plot in Figure 10 visualizes the final locations of the weight vectors associated
 536 with each neuron after training.

Fig. 10: SOM Weight Positions plot showing the final locations of the neurons' weight vectors in the input space. The green points represent the input data, blue circles represent the SOM neurons (weight vectors), and red lines indicate the connections between neighboring neurons.

537 These weight vectors represent positions in the input space that the SOM neurons adjust to fit the
 538 distribution of the input data during training.

539 The proximity of blue circles to green points indicates how well the SOM represents the input data.
 540 Neurons close to dense clusters of green points reflect accurate mapping of data-rich regions, while
 541 sparse regions with fewer neurons show that the SOM has adapted to areas with less data. The red lines
 542 connecting neighboring neurons illustrate the SOM's topological structure, with shorter lines representing
 543 similar regions and longer lines highlighting transitions between clusters or sparse areas.

544 The arrangement of weight vectors in the plot demonstrates how well the SOM has adapted to
 545 the data's structure. Regions with dense clusters of green points typically have neurons (blue circles)
 546 positioned closer together, indicating successful mapping of similar data points. The red lines between

547 neighboring neurons ensure that the topological relationships in the input space are preserved during
 548 the SOM training process.

549 4.3.2 OK Prediction with SOM Neuron Grouping

550 The **OK Estimation with SOM Neuron Grouping** (OK-SOM), as shown in Figure 11, illustrates
 551 the application of OK for predicting zinc concentration across the study area by utilizing SOM to group
 552 the data into neurons.

Fig. 11: OK-SOM showing the spatial distribution of zinc concentration (ppm) across the study area. Values in ppm.

553 This method enables spatial prediction of zinc concentration in ppm after back-transformation from
 554 the log scale. That is, the estimation is made in log scale and then transformed into ppm as shown
 555 in the figure. This plot shows the kriging estimation, where regions with higher zinc concentration are
 556 notably in the central part of the area, indicating possible hot spots of mineralization that merit further
 557 investigation. These areas reflect significant zinc accumulations, indicating favorable geology for mineral
 558 deposits. The areas on the periphery yield lower concentrations, indicating a slight chance of significant
 559 mineralization.

560 With this approach, OK interpolates the zinc concentrations in unsampled locations based on the
 561 spatial autocorrelation of the measured data points, providing continuous predictions for the whole area
 562 under study, even for areas with no direct measurements. Moreover, in this plot, the grid structure is
 563 influenced by the fact that the SOM neuron grouping divides the region into distinct clusters or neurons,
 564 each of which applies kriging. This grouping ensures that the local characteristics of each neuron are
 565 considered in the estimation, enhancing the accuracy and reliability of the predicted zinc concentrations
 566 throughout the region.

567 The plot provides a continuous spatial prediction, which enables the identification of areas with
 568 elevated or reduced zinc concentration. Additionally, it helps in identifying the specific area of interest
 569 for further exploration, especially the areas with high estimated zinc concentrations that may require
 570 closer investigation. OK-SOM indicates the spatial variability in zinc concentration, showing possible
 571 local anomalies and broader regional trends.

572 **Table 5 presents the validation measures derived from LOOCV with OK-SOM. Compared to the**
 573 **range of values (30-7000 ppm), RMSE and MAE are acceptably low. Correlation $\rho = 91\%$ shows a robust**

Table 5: Performance of OK-SOM. RMSE: Root Mean Square Error, MAE: Mean Absolute Error, ME: Mean Error, ρ : Pearson’s correlation coefficient.

Metric	OK-SOM
RMSE (ppm)	490.93
MAE (ppm)	153.26
ME (ppm)	-115.46
ρ	0.91

574 correlation between the observed and predicted values. ME of -115.46 shows a slightly negative bias, at
 575 -1.65% of the range.

576 4.4 Comparisons

577 The engaged methods for the mathematical modeling of the spatial dependencies are compared to provide
 a better overview of the results. Table 6 summarizes the LOOCV metrics for all the methods.

Table 6: Validation measures. RMSE: Root Mean Square Error, MAE: Mean Absolute Error, ME: Mean Error, ρ : Pearson’s correlation coefficient.

Metric	OK	GPR	OK-SOM
RMSE (ppm)	485.79	532.14	490.93
MAE (ppm)	186.97	190.46	153.26
ME (ppm)	-71.9	-95.88	-115.46
ρ	0.76	0.73	0.91

578 The neighborhood selection is different for each method. GPR takes into account the entire data for
 579 each prediction point. OK uses a neighborhood of 300 m, based on the kernel bandwidth (correlation
 580 range). OK-SOM takes as neighbors all the data points in the cluster. All methods produced RMSE of
 581 the same magnitude, with OK achieving slightly better RMSE than the rest. The correlation coefficient
 582 is satisfactory for OK and GPR, with OK showing marginally better results. OK-SOM outperforms
 583 them all with a strong correlation of $\rho = 91\%$. The significant improvement of the last-mentioned metric
 584 highlights the combination of a stochastic approach with a classification method.

585 ME presents an interesting low value for the OK method. Since a non-linear transformation is per-
 586 formed on the data, a bias error is introduced in the back transformation (Goovaerts 1997). This can be
 587 attributed to the benefits of the local OK neighborhood selection, which also explains the lower RMSE
 588 of OK. However, this leads to a contradiction, as the BMU classification system of OK-SOM specifically
 589 assists OK in this regard. So it is a profound insight that the neighborhood selection for the OK pre-
 590 diction supports the ME and thus RMSE. In contrast, the OK-SOM neighborhood selection supports
 591 the correlation of the prediction with the observation. This outcome should be further investigated in
 592 different random fields.

594 4.4.1 Spatial Difference Visualization: OK vs. GPR

595 Figure 12 illustrates the spatial distribution of differences in zinc concentration predictions (in ppm)
 596 between the models generated by OK and GPR. The color bar illustrates that differences range from
 597 approximately zero ppm in the blue areas to values close to 1300 ppm in the dark red areas. Warmer
 598 colors indicate regions with greater differences in predictions. White values indicate that OK and GPR
 599 values were effectively the same (within 0.1 ppm difference). In most of the mines, the differences are
 600 below 30 ppm, but there are substantial differences in the Zinc-rich areas of the mine. Visual comparison
 601 of Figs. 3, 4 shows that the smaller neighborhood used in OK results in less smoothing than the GPR.

602 The differences in predicted zinc concentrations that are observed provide some critical insights into
 603 the performance of each model. GPR gives considerably higher predictions than OK in the central regions
 604 of the study area, where dark red values are present. This pattern indicates that GPR effectively captures
 605 localized variations in zinc concentration, underlining the ability of the model to respond to small-scale
 606 spatial trends. Contrarily, peripheral blue areas exhibit a minimal difference, at which OK’s prediction is
 607 close to GPR’s. This is a consequence of the kriging smoothing effect, compared with the more adaptive
 608 GPR approach.

Fig. 12: Absolute values of Spatial differences in zinc concentration predictions (ppm) between OK and GPR. Values in ppm.

609 4.4.2 Scatter Plot Comparison OK vs. GPR

610 Figure 13 compares OK and GPR predictions with the observed zinc concentrations (ppm). The scatter
 611 plot compares the predictive performance of OK and GPR against the observed zinc concentrations (in
 612 ppm). The $y = x$ **black dashed** line represents perfect prediction and thus serves as a benchmark. OK
 613 performs quite well for lower to moderate concentrations (< 1000 ppm); its predictions are close to
 614 the observed values, which reflects the ability of OK to produce stable and smooth estimates. However,
 615 **OK gives a slight underestimation at higher concentrations (>3000 ppm). On the other hand, GPR is**
 616 **more variable for all concentrations and better reflects localized spatial trends and finer heterogeneity.**
 617 **However, GPR gives a greater underestimation of extreme concentrations (>3000 ppm), as reflected by**
 618 **wider deviations, reflecting a problem in generalizing sparse or highly variable data.** Overall, the scatter
 619 plot highlights the complementary strengths of the methods: OK excels in capturing broader spatial
 620 trends with consistency, while GPR captures detailed variability but may introduce higher uncertainty
 621 for extreme values.

622 4.4.3 Spatial Difference Visualization: OK vs. OK-SOM

623 Figure 14 presents the spatial distribution of absolute prediction differences in zinc concentrations (ppm)
 624 between OK and OK-SOM. The color scale ranges from minor differences (near zero ppm) to substantial
 625 discrepancies (up to 1300 ppm). The visualization underscores the predictive tendencies of the two
 626 methods. OK provides smoother, continuous predictions suited for broader regional analyses, whereas
 627 OK-SOM highlights localized anomalies and spatial clusters.

628 4.4.4 Scatter Plot Comparison OK-SOM vs. OK

629 Figure 15 depicts a scatter plot of OK and OK-SOM against observed zinc concentrations. The predictions
 630 by OK reflect relatively stable and consistent performance for all concentration ranges. There is a slight
 631 **underestimation (negative bias) in the OK-SOM** predictions (shown in Tables 5, 6), especially where the
 632 observed concentrations are greater than 1000 ppm.

Fig. 13: Scatter plot comparing original zinc concentrations (ppm) with predictions from OK and GPR. Blue points: GPR predictions. Red points: OK predictions. Back dashed line: perfect prediction.

Fig. 14: Absolute values of Spatial differences in zinc concentration predictions (ppm) between OK and OK-SOM. Values in ppm.

633 In contrast, the OK-SOM predictions show larger variability, indicating a more detailed mapping
 634 of the data. SOM performs well at lower to moderate concentrations (< 3000 ppm), showing closer
 635 agreement with the observed values and resolving finer spatial trends. This variability reflects the OK-
 636 SOM's ability to account for localized spatial heterogeneity. However, at higher concentrations (> 4000
 637 ppm), the OK-SOM predictions are showing greater deviation from the perfect prediction line, which
 638 explains the slightly elevated RMSE shown in Table 6 compared to OK, as RMSE is affected more by
 639 outliers.

Fig. 15: Scatter plot comparing original zinc concentrations (ppm) with predictions from OK-SOM. Red points: OK predictions. Green points: OK-SOM predictions. Black dashed line: perfect predictions.

640 Overall, the results indicate the complementary strengths of the two methods. While OK gives
 641 smoother and more generalized predictions suitable for broader spatial scales, OK-SOM is superior in
 642 capturing local variability and fine-scale patterns in the data. This duality underlines the added value
 643 of combining these approaches, with OK-SOM providing detailed predictions in data-rich areas and OK
 644 ensuring robust estimates across larger regions.

645 4.5 Uncertainty quantification

646 An essential aspect of natural resources analysis is uncertainty quantification. Both GPR and OK can
 647 produce uncertainty maps, reflecting the variance of the predictions. However, both methods require
 648 Gaussianity for the uncertainty to have a physical meaning (Pavlidis et al. 2015).

649 The logarithmic transform moves the data closer to the normal distribution, as can be seen from
 650 Table 1. The first step of the back-transform is

$$\hat{X}(\mathbf{u}) = \exp(\hat{X}^*(\mathbf{u})), \quad (29)$$

651 Where $\hat{X}^*(\mathbf{u})$ is the estimation of the logarithm of the concentration in the prediction point \mathbf{u} . In
 652 the case of the presence of bias, a bias correction factor B can be used in eq. (29) as

$$\hat{X}(\mathbf{u}) = B \exp(\hat{X}^*(\mathbf{u})). \quad (30)$$

653 (Goovaerts 1997; Hristopoulos 2020)

654 However, while back-transforming the predictions to the original scale works well seamlessly, the same
 655 cannot be said for the Error Variance, as it is additive to the log-transformed value, not the original
 656 value. Thus, if ε is the estimation error, so that the true log-value is

$$X(\mathbf{u}) = \hat{X}^*(\mathbf{u}) + \varepsilon(\mathbf{u})$$

657 rather than $\hat{X}^*(\mathbf{u})$, then under the back-transform,

$$\exp(X^*(\mathbf{u}) + \varepsilon(\mathbf{u})) = \exp(X^*(\mathbf{u})) \exp(\varepsilon(\mathbf{u})) \neq \exp(X^*(\mathbf{u})) + \exp(\varepsilon(\mathbf{u})).$$

658 Hence, it is not possible to map the original scale uncertainty by simply exponentiating the log-scale stan-
 659 dard deviation. Conditional Simulations can be used to create maps of uncertainty, but this was beyond
 660 the scope of this research. For the simulations to effectively capture uncertainty, Gaussian anamorphosis
 661 should be conducted first (Pavlidis et al. 2022).

662 While maps of uncertainty are not included, to give a quantification of the uncertainty of the esti-
 663 mation of each method, relative absolute errors (RAE) have been calculated, as shown in Eq. (31).

$$RAE_i = \frac{|\hat{X}(\mathbf{u}_i) - X(\mathbf{u}_i)|}{X(\mathbf{u}_i)}, \quad i = 1, \dots, n. \quad (31)$$

664 E20 and E80 represent the relative absolute error at specific percentiles, shown in Table 7. In geostatistics,
 665 such percentile relative errors are used to assess the spread and magnitude of errors through quantiles:
 666 E20 as the 20th percentile (the relative absolute error below which 20% of errors lie), E80 as the 80th
 667 percentile (the relative error below which 80% of errors lie).

Table 7: Percentile Relative Errors (E20 and E80) for OK, GPR, and SOM-Grouped Kriging

Metric	OK	GPR	OK-SOM Neurons
E20 (Relative Error at 20th Percentile)	31.59%	32.54%	45.50%
E80 (Relative Error at 80th Percentile)	84.04%	85.31%	92.89%

668 Both OK and GPR exhibit similar performance in terms of percentile errors. GPR shows an E20 of
 669 32.54% and an E80 of 85.31%, while OK achieves an E20 of 31.59% and an E80 of 84.04%. This indicates
 670 that both methods perform comparably in predicting values within these specified percentile ranges.
 671 Considering the results of Table 6, it would be unexpected that OK-SOM would show higher relative
 672 errors. However, as Eq. (31) shows, Relative errors are based on the initial value $X(\mathbf{u}_i)$. Thus, if $X(\mathbf{u}_i)$
 673 is low, a slight deviation in $\hat{X}(\mathbf{u}_i)$ could lead to a higher relative error. As can be seen from Fig. 14,
 674 there are differences in the range of 15 to 50 ppm in areas of low Zinc concentration (30-100 ppm). Thus,
 675 while RMSE is only slightly affected, the relative errors are higher. Furthermore, while OK-SOM has
 676 a better correlation coefficient, it has somewhat higher Mean Error, which would also indicate higher
 677 relative error.

678 5 Conclusions

679 This work presents an overview of research on the integration of geostatistical methods with machine
 680 learning techniques to enhance spatial data modeling of **natural resource reserves**, focusing on OK, GPR,
 681 and SOM. **Several kernels were tested to determine the data spatial dependence, including the novel HCE.**
 682 **In preliminary analysis, the performance of HCE was found to be comparable to the exponential kernel;**
 683 **however, the latter was selected due to its slightly superior cross-validation performance.** The main goal
 684 of enhancing prediction accuracy and quantifying spatial uncertainty was successfully achieved.

685 **Gaussian Process Regression effectively captured the non-linear and complex spatial patterns, yielding**
 686 **satisfactory validation errors. As all methods employed are stochastic-based, GPR produced uncertainty**
 687 **bounds comparable to those of Ordinary Kriging (OK), and slightly narrower than those obtained with**
 688 **SOM-OK. OK also provided satisfactory estimates. Moreover, applying a 300 m search neighborhood in**
 689 **OK helped reduce excessive smoothing in the prediction map.**

690 Self-Organizing Maps introduced a novel clustering approach for spatial data, based on the similarity
 691 between neurons. Combined with kriging, SOM increased the predictability, reflected in a higher corre-
 692 lation coefficient and improved error metrics. Fine-scale anomalies and spatial clustering were captured
 693 more effectively with the presented approach, allowing for improved localized accuracy and a more nu-
 694 anced representation of spatial variability. **An important result from the comparison between OK-SOM**
 695 **and OK, is that OK gives significantly less bias, (ME=-71.9 ppm compared to ME=-115.5 ppm for OK-**
 696 **SOM). At the same time, OK-SOM primarily enhances the ρ , giving significantly better values ($\rho = 91\%$)**
 697 **compared to the other methods that give $\rho = 73\%$ (GPR) and $\rho = 76\%$ (OK).**

698 In conclusion, the methods have different strengths: OK and GPR provide broad and stable predic-
 699 tions, and Self-Organizing Maps enhance localized insight and clustering to deal with complex spatial
 700 patterns. These methods together set up a robust framework for addressing intricate spatial datasets,
 701 balancing accuracy, interpretability, and the representation of spatial variability.

702 **Future work could focus on further uncertainty quantification through conditional simulations, more**
 703 **efficient methods for the Gaussian anamorphosis of the data, as well as exploring more kernels, like the**
 704 **Advanced Harmonic Covariance Estimator.**

705 Acknowledgement

706 The research project is implemented in the framework of H.F.R.I call "Basic research Financing (Hori-
707 zontal support of all Sciences)" under the National Recovery and Resilience Plan "Greece 2.0" funded
708 by the European Union – NextGenerationEU (H.F.R.I. Project Number: 16537).

709 Conflict of Interest

710 The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

711 **References**

- 712 Bação F, Lobo V, Painho M (2005) Self-organizing maps as substitutes for k-means clustering. *Computers*
713 & *Geosciences* 31(5):545–553
- 714 Chiles J P, Delfiner P (2012) *Geostatistics: Modeling Spatial Uncertainty*. Wiley, 2 edition
- 715 Cressie N (1990) The origins of kriging. *Mathematical Geology* 22(3):239–252, ISSN 0882–8121
- 716 Cressie N (1993) *Spatial Statistics*. New York: John Wiley and Sons
- 717 Duvenaud D (2014) Automatic model construction with Gaussian processes. Ph.d. dissertation, Univer-
718 sity of Cambridge
- 719 Geoscience Regulation Office Information Hub (2021) Mineral exploration and mining web applications.
720 Technical report, Department of the Environment, Climate and Communications, accessed: 2025-03-1
- 721 Goovaerts P (1997) *Geostatistics for Natural Resources Evaluation*. Oxford University Press
- 722 Haykin S (2009) *Neural Networks and Learning Machines*. Prentice Hall, 3 edition
- 723 Hengl T, Heuvelink G B M, Stein A (2004) A generic framework for spatial prediction of soil variables
724 based on regression-kriging. *Geoderma* 120(1-2):75–93
- 725 Hristopoulos D T (2020) *Random Fields for Spatial Data Modeling: A Primer for Scientists and Engi-*
726 *neers*. Advances in Geographic Information Science, Springer Netherlands
- 727 Hristopoulos D T (2024) Non-separable covariance kernels for spatiotemporal gaussian processes based
728 on a hybrid spectral method and the harmonic oscillator. *IEEE Transactions on Information Theory*
729 70(2):1268–1283
- 730 Karimi E, Haghighi F, Sheykhfard A, Azmoodeh M, Shaaban K (2023) Self-organized neural network
731 method to identify crash hotspots. *Future Transportation* 3(1):286–295
- 732 Kohonen T (2001) *Self-Organizing Maps*. Springer, 3 edition
- 733 Kohonen T (2005) Intro to som. <http://www.cis.hut.fi/projects/somtoolbox/>, retrieved 2025-06-18
- 734 Kohonen T, Honkela T (2011) Kohonen network. *Scholarpedia* 2(1):1568, bibcode: 2007SchpJ...2.1568K
- 735 Krige D G (1951) A statistical approach to some basic mine valuation problems on the witwatersrand.
736 *Journal of the Chemical, Metallurgical and Mineral Society of South Africa* 52:119–139
- 737 Liu Y, Weisberg R H (2005) Patterns of ocean current variability on the west florida shelf using the
738 self-organizing map. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans* 110(C6)
- 739 Liu Y, Weisberg R H (2011) A review of self-organizing map applications in meteorology and oceanog-
740 raphy. In *Self-Organizing Maps: Applications and Novel Algorithm Design*, 253–272
- 741 Matheron G (1965) Les variables régionalisées et leur estimation: une application de la théorie de fonctions
742 aléatoires aux sciences de la nature. Paris: Masson et Cie, École Nationale Supérieure des Mines de
743 Paris
- 744 Murphy K P (2012) *Machine Learning: A Probabilistic Perspective*. The MIT Press
- 745 Papoulis A (1991) *Probability, Random Variables, and Stochastic Processes*. New York: McGraw-Hill, 3
746 edition
- 747 Pavlides A, Agou V D, Hristopoulos D T (2022) Non-parametric kernel-based estimation and simulation
748 of precipitation amount. *Journal of Hydrology* 612:127988
- 749 Pavlides A, Hristopoulos D T, Roumpou C, Agioutantis Z (2015) Spatial modeling of lignite energy reserves
750 for exploitation planning and quality control. *Energy* 93:1906–1917
- 751 Rasmussen C E, Williams C K I (2006) *Gaussian Processes for Machine Learning*. MIT Press
- 752 Varouchakis E A, Corzo G A, Karatzas G P, Kotsopoulou A (2018) Spatio-temporal analysis of annual
753 rainfall in Crete, Greece. *Acta Geophysica* 66(3):319–328
- 754 Varouchakis E A, Koltsidopoulou M D, Pavlides A (2025) Designing robust covariance models for geo-
755 statistical applications. *Stochastic Environmental Research and Risk Assessment*
- 756 Varouchakis E A, Solomatine D, Corzo Perez G A, Jomaa S, Karatzas G P (2023) Combination of
757 geostatistics and self-organizing maps for the spatial analysis of groundwater level variations in complex
758 hydrogeological systems. *Stochastic Environmental Research and Risk Assessment* 37(8):3009–3020
- 759 Vesanto J, Alhoniemi E (2000) Clustering of the self-organizing map. *IEEE Transactions on Neural*
760 *Networks* 11(3):586–600
- 761 Villmann T, Bauer H U (1998) Applications of the growing self-organizing map. *Neurocomputing*
762 21(1):91–100, ISSN 0925-2312